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ASSESSMENT OF SIGNS & SYMPTOMS, RISK FACTORS AND PRESCRIPTION PATTERN IN ISCHEMIC STROKE PATIENTS: AN OBSERVATIONAL & RETROSPECTIVE STUDY IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Background: Stroke is a significant health issue that affects people worldwide, with a particular impact on the elderly population. The prescribing patterns of neurologists and physicians can shed light on the choice of medications for stroke management and how they are adjusted after a stroke occurs. The incidence of stroke has been increasing in low- and middle-income countries, including India, over the past few decades. Furthermore, the number of stroke survivors has nearly doubled between 1990 and 2010 and is expected to continue to rise in the coming years. This underscores the importance of effective stroke management and prevention strategies. **Objective:** Stroke is the second leading cause of death and a major cause of disability worldwide. As appropriate and safe drug use is a key factor in achieving quality health and accurate healthcare for hospitalized patients So it is necessary to assess the prescription pattern, percentage of each drug used and to find out the most commonly prescribed drugs along with assessing the warning signs and symptoms, uncontrollable and controllable risk factors of stroke in the hospitalized patient. **Method:** A retrospective, observational study was conducted, and the data of 120 patients was collected from the medical record department of BAPS Pramukh Swami Hospital. Patients of age 18 and above with ischemic stroke with or without comorbidities will be selected while patients below the age of 18 years and pregnant women will be excluded from the study. The study was conducted for a period of six months and the data collected was analyzed using statistical methods. **Result:** A total of 120 patients were analyzed during the 6 months study period. The study population consisted of 72 male patients (60%) and 48 female patients (40%) the study found that males have a slightly higher stroke risk compared to females. The highest risk for stroke is in the 60-69 age group (42.5%). The most common signs of stroke patients are arm paresis (55%), leg paresis (53.33%), facial paresis (27.5%), and ataxia (20%) and the most common symptoms of stroke patients are arm weakness (55%), leg weakness (53.33%), speech difficulty (50.83%), general weakness (41.66%), giddiness (39.16%), headache (28.33%), and facial weakness (27.05%). Major controllable risk factors include hypertension (73.33%), diabetes mellitus (45%), dyslipidemia (8.33%), smoking (12%), and alcohol (7%). Among these risk factors, hypertension is more prevalent (73.33%). The current prescribing pattern was the most commonly prescribed thrombolytics drug like alteplase N=5(4.16%), enoxaparin N=84(70%) was the most commonly prescribed anticoagulants drug, a common combination of antiplatelet drugs prescribed in the study was aspirin and clopidogrel, used in N=75(62.05%) of patients aspirin alone was used in N=55(45.83%), atorvastatin was highly prescribed N=108(90%), commonly prescribed class of antihypertensive drugs was CCBs N=49(38%), ARB N=24(18%) and β -blockers N=16(12%). The most commonly prescribed individual drugs were amlodipine n=31(25.83%), telmisartan N=22(18.33%), and nifedipine N=15(12.05%). Among the different classes of anti-diabetic drugs and insulin are prescribed. Insulin-like human act rapid N=26(21.66%) and drug-like glipepride + metformin N=21(17.5%) were most commonly prescribed. Gabapentin N=9(7.50%) was the most prescribed antiepileptic. Drugs used for Alzheimer's are memantine N=09(7.05%) other drugs like antibiotics, steroids, nootropics, antidepressants, antipsychotics, thyroid drugs, multivitamins, PPI and H2 blockers, NSAIDs, and analgesics. **Conclusion** The present study aimed to identify cases with predominant signs and symptoms of stroke, estimate various risk factors and determine the appropriate prescribing pattern of drugs based on stroke severity and associated co-morbid conditions. The study found that arm paresis (55%) and leg paresis (53.33%), were the most common signs of stroke patients. Arm and leg weakness, speech difficulty, general weakness, and giddiness were the most common symptoms reported by patients Recognizing the signs and symptoms of stroke is crucial for minimizing its damage, and seeking immediate medical attention is essential. The study also identified hypertension (73.33%) and diabetes (45%) as the most common risk factors. Managing risk factors such as Hypertension, Diabetes Mellitus, Dyslipidemia, Heart Disease, Smoking, Alcohol, and Obesity for preventing stroke. Additionally, creating awareness among the elderly population about the risk factors associated with stroke can help to reduce the incidence of stroke The study analyzed the prescribing patterns of various drugs for stroke patients. Thrombolytics, such as alteplase, were prescribed in a small number of patients (4.16%), while the most commonly prescribed anticoagulant drug was enoxaparin (70%). Aspirin and clopidogrel were commonly prescribed in combination (62.05%), and aspirin alone was used in (45.83%) of patients. Atorvastatin was highly prescribed (90%) to manage dyslipidemia. Stroke requires a multidisciplinary treatment approach, including medications, rehabilitation, lifestyle modifications, and interventions to prevent future strokes. Prescribing drugs should consider individual patient needs and characteristics Individualized care and adherence to guidelines are essential for stroke management and prevention.

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INTRODUCTION

Stroke is a in 1970 the world health organization defined stroke as “rapidly developed clinical signs of focal (or global) disturbance of cerebral function. Lasting more than 24 hours or leading to death with no apparent cause other than of vascular origin.^[1]

Major cause of mortality worldwide and commonly occurs in elderly patients. Study helped to identify the predominant signs and symptoms, estimate various risk factors and the prescribing pattern of drugs.

We also studied for sign and symptoms of stroke as early detection and treatment of ischemic stroke can help prevent further brain damage. Recognizing the early signs and symptoms of ischemic stroke, such as sudden numbness or weakness in the face, arm, or leg, can help to get medical attention right away. This can help improve chances of recovery and reduce the risk of long-term disability. Study helped to identify the certain controllable stroke risks factors like hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidemia, heart disease, smoking, alcohol, obesity, and uncontrollable risk factors like age, gender, family history of stroke, prior stroke.^[10] We sought to look at the prescribing patterns of neurologists and physicians to identify the choice of a specific agent over another and what changes are made when a stroke occurs in these patients and certain controllable stroke risks factors like hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidemia, heart disease, smoking, alcohol, obesity, and uncontrollable risk factors like age, gender, family history of stroke, prior stroke.^[2]

There has been a more than 100 percent increase in the incidence of stroke in low- and middle-income countries including India from 1970-1979 to 2000-2008.^[3] The number of stroke survivors almost doubled between 1990 and 2010 and has now reached 33 million people. According to epidemiological projections, this number will rise to 77 million by 2030.^[4]

Rationality is of utmost importance because irrational use can lead to misuse, underuse, or overuse of medicines. A major step towards the rational use of medicine was taken in 1977 when they established the model list of essential medicines to assist countries in formulating their essential list^[5]

Medicines are an integral part of health care, and modern health care is impossible without the availability of necessary medicines. They not only save lives and promote health but prevent epidemics and diseases too^[6]

Prescription pattern monitoring studies (PPMS) are a tool for assessing the prescribing, dispensing, and distribution of medicines. The main aim of PPMS is to facilitate the rational use of medicines (RUM).^[7]

It has been highlighted that prescription monitoring studies are imperative to bridge the areas such as rational use of drugs, pharmacovigilance, Pharmacoeconomics, pharmacogenetics, and evidence-based medicine.^[6]

OBJECTIVES:

Primary Objectives

- To assess the prescription pattern of ischemic stroke
- To assess the percentage of each drug used
- To Find out the most commonly prescribed drugs

Secondary Objectives

- To assess the warning signs and symptoms.
- To assess the uncontrollable and controllable risk factors
- To assess and prevent secondary stroke

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY DESIGN AND POPULATION

This was an Observational and retrospective study with 120 population size.

STUDY DURATION

The total duration for the study was 4 months and 2 months for data analysis and data compilation.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted by the ICH-GCP guidelines. Important documents such as protocol, and data collection form like CRF was presented to the Ethics committee for approval of the same. The study proceeded after permission was granted.

This study was designed as a retrospective and observational. This was a single-site study conducted at BAPS pramukh swami hospital, Surat for inpatients diagnosed with ischemic stroke patients in the previous year from May 2021- May 2022. The main aim was the Assessment of signs & symptoms, risk factors & prescription patterns in ischemic stroke patients.

The number of participants in the study included was 120 according to our inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study.

PROCEDURE

The study started by obtaining permission from the Medical Records Department of BAPS Hospital to access the patient files from the previous year's patients diagnosed with ischemic stroke.

Once the permission was granted, the study proceeded by collecting the necessary data from the patient's case sheet into Case Report Form. The data collection included Patients' demographic details, past medical history, social history, signs and symptoms vital parameters, Lab reports, and clinical outcomes with a special focus on prescription patterns of drugs.

Statistical analysis was performed to determine the Assess the prescription pattern of drugs, the percentage of each drug used, and find out the most commonly prescribed drugs.to identify the signs and symptoms, uncontrollable and controllable risk factors prevention of secondary stroke.

STUDY CRITERIA

➤ Inclusion Criteria:

- Patient above 18yrs of age.
- Patient diagnosis is confirmed clinically and Radiologically (CT & MRI scan)
- Patient With or Without Comorbidities
- Patient with identified and unidentified Risk factors.

➤ Exclusion Criteria:

- Patient Below 18yrs of Age
- Pregnant and Lactating Women
- Haemorrhagic Stroke patients
- Patient with Intracranial abnormalities like Brain Tumor.

RESULTS

ASSESSMENT OF SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS OF STROKE PATIENTS

1. Assessment Of Signs:

The four most common signs of stroke patients are arm paresis 55% (N=66), leg paresis 53.33%(N=64), facial paresis 27.5%(N=33), and ataxia 16.66%(N=20). Other less common signs include eye movement abnormality, visual field defect, and hemiparetic gait.

Figure 1: Assessment of Signs of stroke patients.

2. Assessment Of Symptoms:

The seven most common symptoms of stroke patients arm weakness 55% (N=66), leg weakness 53.33%(N=64), speech difficulty 50.83% (N=61), general weakness 41.66%(N=50), giddiness 39.16% (N=47), headache 28.33% (N=34), and facial weakness 27.05%(N=33). Other less common symptoms include arm paresthesia, leg paresthesia, and drowsiness.

Figure 2: Assessment of Symptoms of stroke patients.

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS:

1. Gender:

The study population consisted of 60% male patients (N=72) and 40% female patients (N=48). The mean age of male patients was 63.70 years, while the mean age of female patients was 64.95 years. The study found that males have a slightly higher stroke risk compared to females.

Figure 3: Bar Graph- Gender distribution.

Figure 4: Pie chart- Gender in percentage.

2. Age Group:

Among the enrolled patients, the age group between 50-79 years old was highly affected at 69.16%(N=83) with the highest risk for stroke being in the 60-69 age group 42.5%(N=51). The age group over 80 had a small number of patients 8.33% (N=10). The study found that the risk of having a stroke increases with age after 50.

Figure 5: Bar Graph- Age distribution.

3. Social History:

Included are studies involving 120 subjects according to study criteria. Smoking 12%(N=15) (Cigarettes) was a more important risk factor for stroke than excessive drinking of alcohol 7% (N=8). Both regular alcohol intake and smoking (Cigarettes) 3%(N=4) are strong, unequivocal risk factors for ischemic stroke

Figure 6: Bar Graph- social history.

4. Past Medical History:

According to the study, the most common comorbidities in ischemic stroke patients were: Hypertension 73.33% (N=88), Diabetes 45% (N=54), Dyslipidaemia 08.33% (N=10), Ischemic heart disease 07.05% (N=09), and Hypothyroidism 05% (N=06) and Hyperthyroidism 00.83% (N=01).

Figure 7: Past medical history.

In many stroke patients, more than one comorbidity is present. The most common combination of comorbidities is Hypertension and Diabetes 30% (N=36), followed by Hypertension, Diabetes, and Ischemic heart disease 5.83%(N=07), and Hypertension, Diabetes, and Dyslipidemia 5.00% (N=6).

Figure 8: Combinationpast medical history.

5. Clinical Outcome:

In this study, most of the patients Recovered 86.66% (N=104). Out of the 120 patients, there was a mortality rate of 5% (N=6), and some were discharged with either DAMA 5.83% (N=7) or DOR 2.05% (N=3).

Figure 9: Clinical outcome.

PRESCRIPTIONPATTERN

1. Thrombolytic Agents:

In the study, thrombolytic treatment was only prescribed to 5 subjects (4.16%) out of the 120 subjects. All 5 subjects received alteplase.

THROMBOLYTIC AGENTS		
Drug	Number of patients	Percentage
Alteplase(TPA)	05	04.16%

Table 1: Thrombolytic Agents.

2. Anticoagulant Agents:

Among the anticoagulants used in the study, Enoxaparin 70%(N=84) was the most commonly prescribed drug for stroke patients. The other anticoagulants used were nicoumalone 2.05%(N=3), dabigatran 0.83% (N=1), and warfarin 0.83% (N=1).

Figure 10: Anticoagulants Prescribed in Stroke Patients.

3. Antiplatelet Agents:

The most common combination of antiplatelet drugs prescribed in the study was aspirin and clopidogrel, used in 62.05% (N=75) of patients. Aspirin alone was used in 45.83% (N=55) of patients, while clopidogrel was used in 26.66% (N=32) of patients.

Figure 11: Antiplatelets Prescribed in Stroke Patients.

4. Statins:

In the study, Atorvastatin was the most commonly prescribed antihyperlipidemic drug, used in 90% (N=108) of patients. The second most commonly used drug was Rosuvastatin, used in 5.53% (N=7) of patients.

Figure 12: Statins Prescribed in Stroke Patients.

5. Antihypertensive Agents:

In the study, the most commonly prescribed class of antihypertensive drugs was calcium channel blockers (CCBs) used in 38% of patients. The most commonly prescribed individual drugs were Amlodipine 25.83% (N=31), Telmisartan 18.33% (N=22), and Nifedipine 12.05% (N=15). Other commonly used classes of antihypertensive drugs were angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) 18 (N=24), β -blockers 12% (N=16), diuretics 8% (N=11), α + β -blockers 7% (N=9), α -blockers 6% (N=8), ACE inhibitors 2% (N=2), and combination drugs 9% (N=12).

Figure 13: Antihypertensive Prescribed in Stroke Patient.

6. Anticonvulsants:

In this study, Gabapentin was the most prescribed antiepileptic drug with a percentage of 7.50% (N=9) followed by Levetiracetam 6.66% (N=8), Clonazepam 5% (N=6) and Sodium valproate 3.33% (N=4).

Figure 14: Anticonvulsants Prescribed in Stroke Patients.

7. Antidiabetic:

These are the most prescribed drugs to maintain blood sugar levels. Among the different classes of anti-diabetic drugs and insulin are prescribed. Insulin-like Human actrapid 21.66%(N=26) And Glargine 3.33%(N=4). most common Oral hypoglycemic agents prescribed Glimepiride + Metformin 17.5%(N=21), Metformin5%(N=6), Teneligliptin3.33%(N=4).

Figure 15: Antidiabetic Prescribed in Stroke Patients.

8. Antialzheimer:

In this study, the most prescribed drugs are used for Alzheimer’s. Memantine 07.05% (N=09) Donepezil 04.16%, (N=05), and Donepezil + Memantine 00.83%. (N=01).

Figure 16: Antialzheimer Prescribed in Stroke Patients.

9. Multivitamins:

Multivitamins are vitamins B12, B9, and B6 are used to elevate homocysteine and may increase the risk of stroke, heart attack, and cardiovascular disease.

Drug	Number of patients	Percentage
B12+B9+B6	51	42.05%

Table 2: Multivitamins.

10. Thyroid Drug:

The Drugs Used To Treat Hypothyroidism is Thyroxin6.66% (N=8). Meanwhile, Carbimazole Was Used To Treat Hyperthyroidism1.66% (N=2).

Table 3: Thyroid Drug.

THYROID DRUG		
Disease	Drug	Percentage
Hypothyroidism	Thyroxine	6.66%
Hyperthyroidism	Carbimazole	1.66%

DISCUSSION

Stroke is a serious medical condition that occurs when blood flow to the brain is interrupted, causing brain cells to die. The consequences of stroke can be severe, including paralysis, speech difficulties, and cognitive impairment. As a leading cause of death and disability worldwide, identifying the signs, symptoms, and risk factors of stroke is crucial for developing effective prevention and treatment strategies^[8]

This retrospective study examined data from 120 stroke patients to identify common characteristics and treatment patterns. The study revealed that the proportion of male patients (60%) with stroke was higher than that of female patients (40%). The study found that the age group between 60-79 years (42.5%) was the most affected by stroke, with a higher risk of developing stroke after the age of 60. This finding suggests that creating awareness among the elderly population about the risk factors associated with stroke is crucial. Healthcare providers should educate elderly patients about the importance of managing risk factors such as smoking, which was found to be a more important risk factor than excessive drinking of alcohol.

The study found that arm paresis (55%) and leg paresis (53.33%), were the most common signs of stroke patients. These symptoms may be a result of damage to the motor cortex of the brain, which controls movement. Arm and leg weakness, speech difficulty, general weakness, and giddiness were the most common symptoms reported by patients. These symptoms can be associated with a lack of blood flow to specific regions of the brain.

The study also identified hypertension (73.33%) and diabetes (45%) as the most common comorbidities found in stroke patients. Comorbidities are additional medical conditions that coexist with the primary condition. In this case, hypertension and diabetes are important risk factors for stroke and can increase the likelihood of experiencing a stroke. Managing these comorbidities is critical to prevent the risk of stroke. For example, managing hypertension can help to control blood pressure levels, which is important for preventing the risk of stroke. Similarly, managing diabetes can help to control blood sugar levels, which can reduce the risk of stroke.

Finally, the study examined the prescription patterns of anticoagulants, antiplatelet, antihyperlipidemic, antihypertensive, and antiepileptic drugs. These drugs are commonly used to prevent recurrent strokes or manage comorbidities. For example, anticoagulants and antiplatelets can prevent blood clots from forming, which can cause a stroke. Antihypertensive drugs can help to manage hypertension, and antihyperlipidemic drugs can help to manage hyperlipidemia, both of which are important risk factors for stroke. Managing seizures and maintaining blood sugar levels are also important in preventing recurrent strokes.

The study analyzed the prescribing patterns of various drugs for stroke patients. Thrombolytics, such as alteplase, were prescribed in a small number of patients (4.16%), while the most commonly prescribed anticoagulant drug was enoxaparin (70%). Aspirin and clopidogrel were commonly prescribed in combination (62.05%), and aspirin alone was used in 45.83% of patients. Atorvastatin was highly prescribed (90%) to manage dyslipidemia. Among the different classes of antihypertensive drugs, calcium channel blockers (CCBs), angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), and beta-blockers were commonly prescribed, with amlodipine 25.83% being the most commonly prescribed individual drugs.

The study found that among the different classes of anti-diabetic drugs, insulin-like human act rapid was the most commonly prescribed drug, with a prescription rate of 21.66%. The drug combination of glimepiride + metformin was the second most commonly prescribed anti-diabetic drug, with a prescription rate of 17.5%.

In terms of antiepileptic drugs, gabapentin was the most prescribed, with a prescription rate of 7.5%. For Alzheimer's disease, memantine was the most commonly prescribed drug, with a prescription rate of 7.05%. Other drugs prescribed in the study included antibiotics, steroids, nootropics, antidepressants, antipsychotics, thyroid drugs, multivitamins, PPIs and H2 blockers, NSAIDs, and analgesics. However, the study did not provide detailed information on the prescription rates of these drugs.

However, in some cases, additional medications may be necessary for the management of other medical conditions or stroke-related complications. For example, if a patient with ischemic stroke has high blood pressure, medications may be given to lower blood pressure and prevent further damage to the brain. Similarly, if a patient has an infection, antibiotics may be given to treat the infection^[9]

The loading doses of drugs used for the treatment of ischemic stroke include:

- Anticoagulant or antiplatelet therapy - these medications can help to prevent further blood clots from forming in the brain, which can help to reduce the risk of future strokes. The recommended loading dose of aspirin for acute ischemic stroke is usually 325 mg, although a lower dose of 160-325 mg may also be used. For other antiplatelet agents such as clopidogrel, the loading dose may vary depending on the specific medication and the patient's condition^[9]
- The loading dose of anticoagulant medications may depend on the medication being used. For example, for unfractionated heparin, the loading dose is typically 60 units/kg, while for low molecular weight heparin (LMWH) such as enoxaparin, the loading dose may be 0.5-1 mg/kg. For newer oral anticoagulants such as dabigatran, rivaroxaban, and apixaban, the loading dose may not be necessary.

Overall, this study provides valuable insights into the characteristics and treatment patterns of stroke patients. Healthcare providers can use these findings to create effective treatment plans and prevent the risk of stroke. Managing comorbidities such as hypertension and diabetes is critical for preventing stroke. Additionally, creating awareness among the elderly population about the risk factors associated with stroke can help to reduce the incidence of stroke.

CONCLUSION

The present study helped to identify the cases with predominant signs and symptoms, estimate various risk factors and the prescribing pattern of drugs should be based on the severity of the stroke, and associated co-morbid conditions.

It is important to recognize the signs and symptoms of stroke and seek medical attention as soon as possible to minimize the damage caused by a stroke. Symptoms typically comes suddenly and without any warning, so it is important to seek immediate medical attention by calling emergency services.

Pharmacists can play a crucial role in identifying and managing risk factors for stroke. In addition, pharmacists can provide education and counseling to patients on how to minimize their risk of stroke. This may involve providing information on healthy lifestyle habits such as regular exercise, healthy eating, and smoking cessation, as well as providing education on the importance of medication adherence and monitoring for potential side effects. Work with physicians and other healthcare providers to ensure that patients are receiving optimal therapy based on the latest therapeutic guidelines for stroke management. This may involve providing input on medication selection and dosing, monitoring drug interactions and side effects, and ensuring that patients are receiving appropriate follow-up care.

It is important to note that stroke is a serious medical condition requiring a multidisciplinary treatment approach. This includes medications, rehabilitation, lifestyle modifications, and other interventions to prevent future strokes. Regarding medication use, it is essential to consider each patient's individual needs and characteristics when prescribing drugs. This includes factors such as the type and severity of the stroke, the patient's age, comorbidities, and medication history.

FUTURE RESEARCH

Expanding our research to an intervention study and increasing the sample size can indeed provide valuable insights into the medication related to stroke management. Additionally, increasing the sample size can enhance the statistical power of study. With a larger sample, we can detect smaller treatment effects, reduce the likelihood of chance findings, and increase the generalizability of our results to a broader population. Overall, incorporating intervention studies, increasing sample sizes, and adopting prospective study designs can significantly advance our understanding of medication related to stroke management. These approaches can help generate robust evidence to guide clinical decision-making and potentially improve patient outcomes.

ABBREVIATION

ACE- Angiotensin-converting enzyme;
ARBs - Angiotensin-receptor blockers;
CCBs- Calcium channel blockers;
CFR- Case report form;
CT-Computer tomography;
DAMA- Discharge against medical advice
DM- Diabetes mellitus;
DOR- Discharge on request;
HTN – Hypertension;
ICH-GCP- International Conference on Harmonization-Good clinical practice;
IHD- Ischemic heart disease;
LAMICs- Low and middle-income countries;
LMWH- Low molecular weight heparin;
MRD- Medical Records department;
MRI- medical resonance imaging;
N- Number of patients;
NSAIDs- Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs;
PPI- Proton pump inhibitor;
PPMs- Prescription pattern monitoring;
RUM- Rational use of medicine;
TPA- Tissue plasminogen activator
WHO- world health organization;
 α - Blockers-Alpha Blockers;
 α + β - Blockers-Alpha +Beta Blockers;
 β - Blockers-Beta Blockers.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

Nikunj, Krupa, Bhavna and shrinit for designing and conducting study, analyzing data, interpreting result and drafting manuscript.

Dr. Fatima and Dr. RoshanPatel were involved in supervision of study and its critical review. Final approval of the version to be published is given by all the authors.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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